

EFFECT OF WASTE PLASTIC ON THE PROPERTIES OF ORDINARY BITUMEN

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Abstract

Disposal of plastic waste is a serious threat and also challenging to the environment resulting in global warming and pollution. The use of plastic waste in bituminous concrete mix is not only a solution for the above discussed problem but also improves bituminous mix characteristics and strength. Many researchers have explored the possibilities of using waste plastic in bituminous concrete mix and they found improvement in the performance of the mix. Researchers have also observed that the common defects in pavement such as corrugation, potholes, ruts; etc gets reduced when bituminous concrete mix is prepared by mixing waste plastic. For this study total weight of bitumen was considered as 500 grams and the shredded waste plastic were added in varying percentages (2%, 4%, 6%, 8%, 10% & 12%) by weight of bitumen in hot bitumen. Sisal fiber is also added at the rate of 0.3% by weight of bitumen in the mix to further enhance its property. Various tests such as specific gravity test, penetration test, ductility test, Softening point test and Flash & fire point test were conducted in laboratory on ordinary as well as modified bitumen. The tests result indicate that there is no change in the specific gravity value up to 10% addition of waste plastic after that there is slight increase in value. Penetration value is decreasing by increasing the percentages of waste plastic. Ductility value is increasing and it is maximum at 8% of waste plastic by weight of bitumen beyond that ductility value is decreasing. Softening point and Flash & Fire point values are also decreasing with increased percentages of waste plastic. The result indicates that enhancement in the properties of the ordinary bitumen. Hence it is expected that the use of the modified bitumen (modified with waste plastic and sisal fiber) in the bituminous concrete mix will result in the enhancement of its properties such as strength and durability.

Keywords: Waste plastic, Sisal fiber, Penetration, Ductility, Softening point

1. Introduction

Every year a huge quantity of waste plastic are being generated in India as well as all over the world. Plastic use in our country is expected to hit 15 million, with half of that used for packaging. India produces 5.6 million metric tonnes of plastic waste every year, with Delhi producing the most. According to a survey report from Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), the majority of the waste which is approximately 689.5 metric tonnes per day is produced from municipality wastes. The disposal of such waste plastics is a major issue faced

all over the world. The disposal of waste plastic imposes major threats to the environment. The use of waste plastic in road construction is one of the solutions for mitigation of its disposal issue. In this study waste plastics from plastic carry bags, milk pouch, and wrapper are used. Many research works have already been carried out by researchers in this area. Sulochana T (2016) did experimental investigations on the bitumen modified with plastic waste and they have noticed the increase in the strength of bitumen. G. Ramesh kumar (2017) studied on partial replacement of bitumen with waste plastic and polypropylene in road construction. In the present paper an attempt has been made to study the effect of waste plastic and sisal fiber on the properties of ordinary bitumen. Based on the reviewed literatures objective of the study has been framed out and mentioned in the subsequent paragraph.

1.1 Objective of the Study: In this paper an attempt has been made to find out the effect of waste plastic on the properties of ordinary bitumen. The objective of the present study is mentioned below:

- To study the effect of waste plastic and sisal fiber on the properties of ordinary bitumen.
- To determine optimum percentage of waste plastic to get most suitable modified bitumen.

1.2 Scope of the Study:

Based on the objective, scope of the study is framed out as discussed below:

- Collection of ordinary bitumen, waste plastic, sisal fiber.
- Shredding of waste plastic.
- To find out the physical properties of ordinary bitumen and modified bitumen prepared with mixing of waste plastic and sisal fiber in varying percentages.
- Comparison of the results and recommendation of most suitable modified bitumen for using in bituminous concrete pavement.

2. Literature Review:

G. Ramesh Kumar et al (2017) did experimental study on partial replacement of bitumen with waste plastic and polypropylene in road construction. They have used waste plastic and polypropylene in varying percentages of 1, 3, 5, & 7% of weight of bitumen. They found that water resistivity, capacity and Stability of the mixes were increased. They found that decrease in penetration, ductility value and increase in softening point, flash & fire point and Stability value of the mix.

Utibe J. Nkanga et al (2017) studied on characterization of bitumen/ plastic blends for flexible pavement application. They have added different proportions (5, 10, &15%) of polymeric materials with bituminous mix and performed various tests such as Marshall Stability test, water absorption test, bulk density. They found that bitumen/plastic blend has higher Marshall Stability, lower bulk density and Marshall Flow as compared to normal mix. Amit kundal & Amit Goel (2019) studied of bituminous mixes with sisal fiber. They have added sisal fiber in bituminous mix in varying percentages (0-0.8%) and found 0.4% as

optimum fiber content. Various tests such as Marshall Stability and drain down were conducted. They found that with the addition of sisal fiber in bituminous mixes Marshall Stability value and durability increases, whereas Flow value and percentage air void decreases.

Kandlagunta mounika et al (2018) studied of bituminous mixes using sisal fiber. They have used sisal fiber as stabilizer in stone matrix asphalt and as additive in bituminous concrete. Varying percentage of sisal fiber (0 to 0.5%) and binder content (4 to 7%) by weight of mix was used to find out optimum bitumen & sisal fiber content. They found optimum fiber content and optimum binder content as 0.3% and 5% respectively by using Marshall Method. They concluded that properties like Marshall Stability, Drain down and indirect tensile strength improved with the addition of sisal fiber.

3. Methodology Adopted:

The plastics were shredded and blended with the bitumen with a mechanical stirrer at a temperature range of 160 °C–170 °C. In the present study, detailed literatures were reviewed related to the topic and some of them are presented above. Experimental investigations carried out in the present study presented here. Different materials used for this project work, including details of test conducted in the laboratory are also discussed.

3.1 Material used:

3.1.1 Waste plastic:

Poly-ethylene, polystyrene, polypropylene are the types of plastic which is obtained from different sources like plastic carry bags, milk pouch, wrapper are used in this work. Shredded waste plastic is mixed with hot bitumen which improves bituminous properties. Use of waste plastic in this research is passing through 4.75 mm IS sieve retained on 2.36 mm sieve. Specific gravity and melting point are found to be 1.05 and 160-210 °C respectively. Locally available waste plastic is used shown in figure 1

Figure 1: Shredded waste plastic

3.1.2 Sisal fiber:

The sisal fiber is mainly used in paper, cloths, footwear, bags, rope, geo-textiles, etc. It is also used as fiber reinforcement for composite fiber glass, cement and rubber products. In this project work sisal fiber is used to enhance the property of bituminous mix. Diameter and length of the sisal fiber used in this thesis work is 0.25mm and 50mm respectively. From the

literature specific gravity of sisal fiber is found to be 0.71. A sample sisal plant and fiber is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Sisal plant and fiber

3.1.3 Ordinary bitumen:

Bitumen is a material which is a byproduct of petroleum refining process. It is a highly viscous at temperature above 100 degrees Celsius and is solid at room temperature. In this study 80/100 grade bitumen is used. Various tests such as Penetration, ductility, softening point, specific gravity flash & fire point were conducted.

3.1.4 Modified Bitumen:

The ordinary bitumen was modified using sisal fiber and waste plastic. For this purpose, the weight of the ordinary bitumen was considered as 500 gm where as sisal fiber was added at 0.3% of bitumen weight and waste plastic was added in varying percentages of weight of bitumen. The details of mix proportion for modifying bitumen are given in Table 1 and the process is shown in figure 3.

Table 1: Mix proportion of Modified Bitumen

Mix Abbreviation	Percentage of Sisal Fiber	Percentage of Waste Plastic
MB1	0.3	2
MB2	0.3	4
MB3	0.3	6
MB4	0.3	8
MB5	0.3	10
MB6	0.3	12

Figure 3: Heating of Bitumen and Mixing of Waste plastic and sisal fiber

3.2 Numerical Study:

Various tests conducted on ordinary as well as modified bitumen is described below-

3.2.1 Tests on ordinary bitumen:

3.2.1.1 Penetration Test:

Penetration test is conducted for classifying the grades of binder. This test check the depth to which a Penetrometer needle would like to penetrate vertically under specified temperature and load. So the main function of this test is to measure the penetration of a standard needle in a given bitumen sample for 5 second at maintained room temperature 25°C. The test result is given in Table 2 and also shown in figure 4.

Table 2: Penetration Test Result

Penetrometer Dial Readings	I	II	III	Mean Value
(i) Initial Reading	100	186	270	-
(ii) Final Reading	186	270	354	-
Penetration value	86	84	82	84

Figure 4: Penetration Test

The penetration value comes out to be 84 mm.

3.2.1.2 Ductility Test:

The ductility of bitumen is estimated by the distance in cm that it lengthens prior to breaking when a standard briquette test of the material is isolated at a predetermined speed and temperature. The test result is given in Table 3 and also shown in figure 5.

Table 3: Ductility Test Result

Observations	Mould number			Mean Ductility Value
	I	II	III	
Observation 1	91.40	89.50	91.63	90.84
Observation 2	88.30	90	86.24	88.18

Figure 5: Ductility test

Mean value of ductility = 89.51 cm

3.2.1.3 Softening Point Test:

Softening point is a temperature at which bituminous material attains a particular degree of softening. Test results are given in Table 4 and shown in figure 6

Table 4: Softening Point Test Result

Temperature when ball touches bottom surface of plate in °C	Ball 1	Ball 2
		42.4
Average Temperature	43.3°C	

Figure 6: Softening Point test setup

Average Softening point Temperature = 43.5°C (Nearest to 0.5°C)

3.2.1.4 Specific gravity Test:

Specific gravity is defined as the ratio of the mass of a given volume of the bituminous material to the mass of an equivalent volume of water at the temperature of 27°C. The specific gravity of bitumen varies from 0.97 to 1.02. Test results are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Specific Gravity Test Result

Weights				Specific Gravity = (C-A)/[(B-A)-(D-C)]
Pycnometer(A)	Pycnometer + Water, (B)	Pycnometer + Bitumen, (C)	Pycnometer + Water + Bitumen (D)	
(gm)	(gm)	(gm)	(gm)	
22.276	74.150	55.442	74.625	1.01

Specific Gravity of Ordinary Bitumen is 1.01

3.2.1.5 Flash & Fire point Test:

Flash and fire point test is safety tests conducted on bituminous materials so that it gives an indication of the critical temperature at and above where precautions should be taken to eliminate fire hazards during its application. Results are given in Table 6 and shown in figure 7.

Flash point- The flash point of the material is the lowest temperature at which the vapor of substance momentarily text fire in the form of class under a specified condition of test.

Fire point- The fire point is the lowest temperature at which the material gets ignited and burns under a specified condition of test.

Table 6: Flash and Fire point Test Results

Time (minutes)	Temperature (°C)	Remarks
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15	269	
15.4	280	Flash Point
16	292	
17	300	
17.6	304	Fire Point

Figure 7: Flash and Fire point Test

3.2.2 Tests on modified bitumen:

3.2.2.1 Penetration Test:

Penetration test mainly used to check the hardness and softness of bitumen. Test results are given in Table 7.

Table 7: Penetration Test Result

Mix Abbreviation	Penetrometer Dial Readings	I	II	III	Mean Value
MB1	(i) Initial Reading	80	163	244	-
	(ii) Final Reading	163	244	326	-
	Penetration value	83	81	82	82
MB2	(i) Initial Reading	20	97	176	
	(ii) Final Reading	97	176	254	
	Penetration value	77	79	78	78
MB3	(i) Initial Reading	10	86	161	
	(ii) Final Reading	86	161	238	
	Penetration value	76	75	77	76
MB4	(i) Initial Reading	30	106	181	
	(ii) Final Reading	106	181	255	
	Penetration value	76	75	74	75
MB5	(i) Initial Reading	40	113	184	
	(ii) Final Reading	113	184	259	
	Penetration value	73	71	75	73
MB6	(i) Initial Reading	50	119	191	
	(ii) Final Reading	119	191	263	

	Penetration value	69	72	72	71
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3.2.2.2 Ductility Test:

The ductility of a material is the capacity of that material to go through plastic deformation before the break of that material. Test results are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Ductility Test Result

Mix Abbreviation	Observations	Mould Number			Mean Ductility (cm)	Average Ductility (cm)
		I	II	III		
MB1	Observation I	92.20	91.35	93.60	92.38	92.3
	Observation II	90.25	94.42	92.17	92.28	
MB2	Observation I	92.40	95.50	94.00	93.96	94
	Observation II	93.26	94.48	94.38	94.04	
MB3	Observation I	100.5	101	99.36	100.28	99.7
	Observation II	99.70	98.65	99.01	99.12	
MB4	Observation I	101.3	100.8	100.5	100.9	101
	Observation II	102.2	100.4	100.7	101.1	
MB5	Observation I	97.20	98.84	98.29	98.11	98.5
	Observation II	98.94	97.63	100.1	98.89	
MB6	Observation I	94.15	95.32	93.87	94.44	94.3
	Observation II	93.52	95.18	93.78	94.16	

3.2.2.3 Softening Test:

Softening point is a temperature at which bituminous material attains a particular degree of softening. Test results are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Softening Point Test Result

Mix Abbreviation	Temperature when ball touches bottom surface of plate in °C		Average Temperature (°C)
	Ball 1	Ball 2	
MB1	45.36	47.08	46.22
MB2	49.92	47.50	48.71
MB3	49.76	52.64	51.20
MB4	52	54.02	53.01
MB5	58.94	61.12	60.03
MB6	63.09	61.73	62.41

3.2.2.4 Flash & Fire point Test:

Flash and fire point test is safety tests conducted on bituminous materials so that it gives an indication of the critical temperature at and above where precautions should be taken to eliminate fire hazards during its application. Test results are given in Table 10.

Table 10: Flash & Fire point Test Results

Time (min)	Temperature (°C)					
	MB1	MB2	MB3	MB4	MB5	MB6
0	24	24	24	24	24	24
5	51	45	44	40	39	38
10	108	84	99	78	76	74
15	270	257	263	240	247	234
15.6	283 Flash Point	272	275	257	261	250
16	296	287 Flash Point	286	270	274	263
16.2	301	295	292 Flash Point	277	280	270
16.8	311 Fire Point	310	311	296 Flash Point	300 Flash Point	292
17.2		318 Fire Point	323 Fire Point	311	315	305 Flash Point
17.6				329 Fire Point	328	320
17.8					336 Fire Point	327
18.2						342 Fire Point

4. Results:

The details of laboratory investigations carried out for the present study is presented above under serial number 3.2. Results obtained from the laboratory investigations are presented and discussed below.

4.1 Physical Properties of ordinary and modified bitumen:

Various tests were conducted to find out physical properties of ordinary and modified bitumen. The details are mentioned above under serial number 3.2. The test results are again reproduce for comparison purpose and given in Tables 11 to 14 and also shown in figures 8 to

Table 11: Penetration (in mm)

Mix Abbreviation	Percentage waste plastic	Percentage sisal fiber	Penetration value in mm (80/100)
OB	0	0.0	84

MB1	2	0.3	82
MB2	4	0.3	78
MB3	6	0.3	76
MB4	8	0.3	75
MB5	10	0.3	73
MB6	12	0.3	71

Figure 8: Penetration vs % waste plastic

It can be seen from the above table, the penetration value of modified bitumen is getting reduced with the increasing percentage of waste plastic. The variation is from 84 to 71mm. The maximum value of penetration is obtained as 84mm for ordinary bitumen. The minimum penetration value is obtained as 71mm for modified bitumen at 0.3% of sisal fiber and 12% of waste plastic. That means the bitumen is getting harder with the increased percentage of waste plastic.

Table 12: Ductility (in cm)

Mix Abbreviation	Percentage waste plastic	Percentage sisal fiber	Ductility value (cm)
OB	0	0.0	89.51
MB1	2	0.3	92.33
MB2	4	0.3	94.00
MB3	6	0.3	99.70
MB4	8	0.3	101.0
MB5	10	0.3	98.50
MB6	12	0.3	94.30

Figure 9: Ductility vs % waste plastic

From the above table, it can be seen that addition of waste plastic in bitumen increases its ductility till 8% of waste plastic by weight of the bitumen. At more than 8%, the ductility value decreases. The increase in ductility value may be due to interlocking of plastic molecules with bitumen. While reduction in ductility value after 8% might be due to excess plastic waste which makes bitumen stiffer. It is observed that addition of waste plastic up to 8% in construction of flexible pavement give good ductility. It can also be seen that without waste plastic ductility is 89.51 cm. While with addition of waste plastic and sisal fiber ductility increases to 101 cm in case of mix M4 and the increment is 12.83% with respect to the ordinary bitumen.

Table 13: Softening point (in °C)

Mix Abbreviation	Percentage waste plastic	Percentage sisal fiber	Softening point test results (°C)
OB	0	0.0	43.31
MB1	2	0.3	46.22
MB2	4	0.3	48.71
MB3	6	0.3	51.20
MB4	8	0.3	53.01
MB5	10	0.3	60.03
MB6	12	0.3	62.41

Figure 10: Softening point vs % waste plastic

From the above table, it can be seen that with addition of waste plastic from 2%-12%, softening point of the bitumen mixes is increasing compared to the ordinary bitumen. Maximum softening value comes out to be 62.41°C at 12% waste plastic and 0.3% sisal fiber. Increment is 44.10% with respect to the ordinary bitumen.

Table 14: Flash and fire point (in °C)

Mix Abbreviation	Percentage waste plastic	Percentage sisal fiber	Flash point (°C)	Fire point (°C)
OB	0	0.0	280	304
MB1	2	0.3	283	311
MB2	4	0.3	287	318
MB3	6	0.3	292	323
MB4	8	0.3	296	329
MB5	10	0.3	300	336
MB6	12	0.3	305	342

Figure 11: Flash & fire point vs % waste plastic

From the above table it can be seen that with addition of waste plastic from 2-12% in bitumen flash point and fire point both are increasing. Minimum flash value without waste plastic and sisal fiber is 280°C and maximum flash value with waste plastic and sisal fiber is 305°C. Increment is 8.9% with respect to ordinary bitumen. Similarly Fire point is also increasing with increase in percentage of waste plastic. Minimum fire point is 304°C without waste plastic and sisal fiber. Maximum fire point is 342°C at 12% of waste plastic and 0.3% sisal fiber. Increment is 12.5% with respect to the ordinary bitumen.

5. Conclusions:

From the test results obtained from the experimental investigations, following conclusions can be drawn:

5.1 Conclusion on the properties of modified bitumen:Penetration value-

Penetration values of modified bitumen were found to be getting reduced with the increasing percentages of waste plastic. Penetration value for 80/100 grade ordinary bitumen was found as 84 mm which was reduced to 71mm at 12% waste plastic and 0.3% sisal fiber by weight of bitumen. That means the bitumen is getting harder with the increased percentage of waste plastic. Lower grade bitumen is used in hot climatic region. It provides higher resistance to deformation at high temperature. So in the absence of lower grade bitumen, modified bitumen can be used in the hot climatic condition.

Ductility-

For ordinary bitumen ductility was found as 89.51 cm. With addition of waste plastic and sisal fiber ductility increases to 101 cm in case of mix MB4 (Modified bitumen with 8% waste plastic and 0.3% sisal fiber) and the increment is 12.83% with respect to the ordinary bitumen. With high ductility value, the coating of aggregate with bitumen will be more improved in proper which in turn improve the interlocking between the aggregates. Hence the strength of the bituminous concrete mix much improved.

Softening point-

For ordinary bitumen softening point was found as 43.31°C. Softening point was found to be increased with addition of waste plastic and sisal fiber. Maximum softening value comes out to be 62.41°C at 12% waste plastic and 0.3% sisal fiber. Hence the increment is more than 40% with respect to the ordinary bitumen. Higher is the softening point lower will be the temperature susceptibility. So modified bitumen can be used in hot climatic region.

Flash and fire point-

Flash and fire point of ordinary bitumen were found to be 280°C & 304°C respectively. Flash and fire point both are increasing with the addition of waste plastic and sisal fiber. Maximum Flash and fire point value comes out to be 305°C & 342°C respectively at 12% waste plastic and 0.3% sisal fiber. Increment in Flash and fire point is 8.9% & 12.5% respectively. At high temperature bitumen becomes volatiles and catches fire which is very hazardous. So in hot climatic region use of modified bitumen will be beneficial.

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